

effect between photoperiod and temperature could be adapted to wider areas because a high temperature can complement the insufficiency of

photoperiod in low latitudes and a longer photoperiod can complement the inefficiency of temperature in high latitudes. The ideal type of sterile line for

hybrid rice production has a low CFP, a high CSP, a wide TRPS, and a high intensity of supplementary effect between light and temperature. □

The relationship of photosensitivity and sterility in photosensitive genic male sterile (PGMS) lines

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PGMS rice was first discovered in a field of Nongken 58S, a photoperiod-sensitive japonica variety. Photoperiod controls both the development and the pollen fertility of Nongken 58S. Most PGMS lines were photoperiod-sensitive; photoperiod-insensitive sterile lines derived from Nongken 58S became thermosensitive sterile lines. We wanted to breed PGMS lines that are photoperiod insensitive to flowering induction.

We crossed Mudanjiang 8, a photoperiod-insensitive variety, with Nongken 58S. We selected sterile plants with short growth durations from the F₂. From the F₉, we selected the sterile line E85S. We planted it and its parents in 1990 under short day (SD) 10 h light/d, and long day (LD) 14.5 h light/d conditions to observe growth duration and pollen fertility percent (see table).

E85S is insensitive to photoperiod for flowering induction as is Mudanjiang 8, and is sensitive to photoperiod in its fertility alteration, like Nongken 58S. These results indicate that different genes control photosensitive sterility and photosensitive flowering induction and they can be recombined in new types of PGMS lines. □

Fertility and photosensitivity of E85S and its parents. China, 1991.

	Nongken 58S	Mudanjiang 8	E85S
SD heading promotion rate ^a	38.5	-3.4	2.0
Photoperiod sensitivity	Strong	Weak	Weak
Days from sowing to heading with at least 14.5 h of light/d	104	59	58
Maturity type	Late	Early	Early
Fertile pollen (%)			
In SD	70.2	77.4	65.6
In LD	0.0	76.8	0.0

$$^a\text{SD heading promotion rate} = \frac{d \text{ from sowing to heading in LD} - d \text{ from sowing to heading in SD}}{d \text{ from sowing to heading in LD}} \times 100.$$

Identification of CMS lines for hybrid rice development under northern Indian conditions

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We evaluated 13 cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines for adaptability and stability for pollen sterility under the subhumid tropical conditions of western UP in northern India. V20 A, which originated from China, and IR62829 A and IR58025 A, which originated from IRRI, were obtained from the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad. PMS-1 through PMS-10 originated from Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Kapurthala. We planted 5-row plots of each line on 16 Jul 1991 under strict isolation, using *Sesbania* spp. as a physical barrier. Data were recorded for

Performance of CMS lines at Pantnagar, India, during 1991 wet season.

CMS line	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Pollen sterility (%)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Stability
V20 A	81	72.6	100.0	100.0	Stable
IR62829 A	93	71.7	99.7	99.1	Needs purification
IR58025 A	99	81.0	100.0	99.9	Stable
PMS-1	109	64.1	100.0	100.0	Stable
PMS-2	102	63.6	100.0	99.7	Stable
PMS-3	109	70.8	98.4	99.9	Unstable
PMS-4	113	64.8	99.4	99.9	Needs purification
PMS-5	113	66.0	100.0	100.0	Stable
PMS-6	114	66.2	98.1	100.0	Unstable
PMS-7	109	74.6	95.1	100.0	Unstable
PMS-8	109	64.4	100.0	99.9	Stable
PMS-9	113	79.0	86.2	100.0	Unstable
PMS-10	107	69.5	100.0	100.0	Stable

days to 50% flowering, plant height, percent pollen sterility, and percent spikelet fertility, for which we used the mean of 25 panicles.

We identified several stable CMS lines with varying duration and plant type (see table). V20 A, IR58025 A, PMS-1 A, PMS-2 A, PMS-5 A, PMS-8 A, and PMS-10 A had complete pollen sterility and almost 100% spikelet sterility. In

contrast with earlier observations, IR62829 A had slight fertility of pollen and spikelets, possibly because of a different seed source.

These stable lines all had very short stature (63.6-72.6 cm), except IR58025 A, which had semidwarf stature (81.0 cm). V20 A had early duration, IR58025 A and PMS-2 mid-early, and others, medium to mid-late. Observations at

PAU indicated PMS lines had mid-early duration (104-106 d); seed set percentage ranged from 8.2 (PMS-2 A) to 18.5% (PMS-10 A). □

Yield potential

Hormonal signals from root to shoot in xylem sap of rice plants in drying soil

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We compared changes in soil moisture and root water status in horizontally divided, differentially treated root systems of rice plants with changes in leaf water potential, leaf conductance, contents of free and bound abscisic acid (ABA), and cytokinins in the shoot xylem. ABA is a hormone that signals water deficit in soil and closes stomata. Cytokinins are antagonists of ABA as regards stomatal closure.

Seeds of rice cultivar IR36 were sown in sandy loam with 48% humus and raised in growth chambers. Seedlings were transplanted 3 wk after sowing in small plastic pots that fit into a Scholander chamber. We allowed roots that protruded from the bottom of the pots to grow in nutrient solution in beakers below the pots. Three weeks after transplanting, three stress treatments were started: 1) soil and protruding roots kept moist (control), 2) soil unwatered, but protruding roots kept moist, and 3) both soil and protruding roots unwatered for 30 h (water-stressed plants). Soil and protruding roots from treatment 3 were rewatered after 30 h.

Contents of free and bound ABA and cytokinins (2iP + 2iPA and t-Z + t-ZR equivalents) in xylem sap of well-watered, water-stressed, and rewatered rice seedlings.

Treatment	Free ABA (pmol/ml)	Bound ABA (pmol/ml)	2iP + 2iPA equivalent (pmol/ml)	t-Z + t-ZR equivalent (pmol/ml)
Well-watered	7.2 ± 1	73 ± 7.5	3.7	0.9
Water-stressed	92 ± 3	499 ± 75	0.8	0.2
Rewatered	52 ± 12	87 ± 5.7	1.9	0.3

Treatment 2 reduced soil moisture from 30 to 14% within 96 h, but did not alter leaf ψ_w (see figure). When soil moisture decreased below 14%, leaf and stem ψ_w sharply declined, indicating the onset of drought stress. Although the water potential of the shoot did not change when soil moisture ranged from 30 to 14%, leaf conductance decreased by about 50%. This decrease was inversely related to the content of free ABA in the xylem which was measured by radioimmunoassay. The increase of ABA in the xylem probably was root-sourced because the shoot was not drought-stressed during this phase of soil drying.

Prolonged (96-144 h) soil drying from 14 to 6% soil moisture resulted in a further decline in conductance, accompanied by a further threefold increase in ABA. At this stage the shoot was under drought stress. The additional ABA presumably was formed in the shoot and redistributed within the whole plant via phloem and xylem.

Xylem sap contained considerable amounts of bound ABA, the level of which increased during soil drying (treatment 3) and decreased again with rewatering (see table). In contrast, cytokinin levels (isopentenyladenine + isopentenyladenosine equivalents and trans-zeatin + trans-zeatinriboside equivalents [2 iP + 2iPA and t-Z + t-ZR equivalents]), measured by an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay, decreased during soil drying and increased again after rewatering. As cytokinins promote stomatal opening, their quantitative change may also explain observed changes in conductance.

The results provide evidence that rice roots sense soil moisture and send ABA as a hormonal signal to the shoot, which reacts by closing the stomata, and cytokinins as a hormonal signal to open

Changes in leaf conductance, leaf and stem water potential, and xylem ABA content of rice seedlings with upper roots in drying soil and lower roots in water.

stomata. Stomatal closure in response to ABA, and possibly by other adaptive processes, occurs before shoot water deficit develops. Further studies are necessary to elucidate the mechanism of root-to-shoot communication in rice under field conditions. □

Performance of *Oryza sativa* L. varieties under upland field conditions in Papua New Guinea (PNG)

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We evaluated rice genotypes Tambu (Senis/C12), Wantok (Senis/C22), Niupela (a selection from E1 from Indonesia), Senis (a selection from IR20), BR12-5-5-1-1 (developed in PNG), NG8297 (IR9728-2-2-2-2), NG8304 (IR13429-196-1-20), NG8313 (IR46), NG8315 (IR54), and NG8321 (IR4744-295-2-3) under upland field conditions during 1991 in Markham Valley, Morobe Province, PNG.